

1 Droop model identification via model-based design of
2 experiments to describe microalgae nitrogen uptake in
3 continuous photobioreactors

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7
8 **Abstract**

9 The comprehension of nutrients uptake and exploitation dynamics is a key aspect to
10 increase the efficiency and the environmental sustainability of microalgal production at
11 industrial scale. The Droop model is suitable for the description of the effect of nutrients
12 on microalgal growth, but presents challenges in parameter identification due to the
13 high correlation between parameters and the significant experimental effort required.
14 Model-based design of experiments is employed to plan information-rich experiments
15 for precise parameters estimation, based on dynamic variations of dilution rate and
16 nitrogen concentration in a continuous photobioreactor growing microalga
17 *Tetradismus obliquus*. It is shown that only two optimal experiments of 8 days each are
18 sufficient to attain a statistically satisfactory estimation of all model parameters, thus
19 minimising time and resources. Validation experiments show that the model can capture
20 nitrogen uptake dynamics effectively, and demonstrate that the design of optimal
21 dynamic experiments allows calibrating the Droop model rapidly, making it a valuable
22 tool for the study of nutrients dynamics in continuous microalgal cultivation systems.

23
24 **Keywords:** Model-based design of experiments (MBDoe); *Scenedesmus obliquus*;
25 *Tetradismus obliquus*; limiting nutrient internal quota; parameter estimation

28 **Nomenclature**

29 *Abbreviations:*

30 CSTR: continuous stirred-tank reactor

31 MBDoE: Model-based design of experiments

32 OD: optical density

33 OD₇₅₀: optical density at a wavelength of 750 nm

34 PBR: photobioreactor

35

36 *Symbols:*

37 α : constant term of the variance error model

38 $\Delta\%$: percentage perturbation of the parameter

39 θ : vector of model parameters to be estimated

40 $\hat{\theta}$: vector of model parameter estimates

41 $\sigma_{y_i}^2$: variance of the measured response

42 τ : total duration of the experiment

43 ϕ : experiment design vector

44 ϕ^{opt} : final designed experiment

45 k : vector of constants of the model

46 N_θ : number of model parameters

47 N_k : number of model constants

48 N_{sp} : number of sampling times

49 N_x : number of model state variables

50 N_y : number of measured response variables

51 N_u : number of model inputs

52 Q_i : sensitivity matrix of the i^{th} response variable

53 t_{sp} : vector of sampling times

54 u : set of time-varying inputs

55 V : parameter variance-covariance matrix

56 s_{ij} : element (i, j) of the inverse of the experimental error variance-covariance matrix

- 57 $s_{i,p}(t)$: dynamic sensitivity for the i^{th} variable perturbed by the p^{th} parameter at time
58 t
- 59 t_i : t -value of the i^{th} parameter
- 60 \mathbf{x} : vector of the model state variables
- 61 $\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t)$: vector of time derivatives
- 62 $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$: vector of measured response variables
- 63 $\hat{y}_{i,p}^{pert}(t)$: perturbed response value after variation in the p^{th} parameter
- 64 $\hat{y}_{i,REF}$: reference response value for normalisation
- 65
- 66 *Variables:*
- 67 μ (d^{-1}): specific biomass growth rate
- 68 μ_{max} (d^{-1}): maximum specific biomass growth rate
- 69 ρ ($g_N g_x^{-1} d^{-1}$): nitrogen uptake rate
- 70 ρ_N ($g_N g_x^{-1} d^{-1}$): maximum nitrogen uptake rate
- 71 $c_{N,in}$ ($g_N m^{-3}$): concentration of nitrogen at the inlet
- 72 $c_{N,out}$ ($g_N m^{-3}$): concentration of nitrogen at the outlet
- 73 c_x ($g_x m^{-3}$): biomass concentration
- 74 D (d^{-1}): dilution rate
- 75 I ($\mu mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$): light intensity
- 76 I_0 ($\mu mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$): incident light intensity
- 77 I_{opt} ($\mu mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$): optimal light intensity
- 78 k_a ($m^{-2} g_x^{-1}$): biomass light absorption coefficient
- 79 k_d (d^{-1}): specific decay rate
- 80 K_I ($\mu mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$): half-saturation light constant
- 81 K_N ($g_N m^{-3}$): limiting nitrogen half-saturation constant
- 82 q ($g_N g_x^{-1}$): internal nitrogen quota in the cell
- 83 q_{min} ($g_N g_x^{-1}$): minimum nitrogen quota
- 84 q_{max} ($g_N g_x^{-1}$): maximum nitrogen quota
- 85 r_x ($g_x m^{-3} day^{-1}$): local biomass growth rate at coordinate z
- 86 r_x^{avg} ($g_x m^{-3} day^{-1}$): average biomass growth rate

87 W (m): culture depth

88 z (m): spatial coordinate along the thickness of the reactor

89

90

91 **1. Introduction**

92 Autotrophic microalgae and cyanobacteria present a wide spectrum of applications,
93 ranging from the production of biofuels, pigments, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals
94 to their use as fertilisers, aquaculture feed or wastewater treatment. Thanks to their
95 ability to fix CO₂ and to consume inorganic nitrogen and phosphorous from wastewater,
96 their utilisation offers a sustainable approach for multiple industrial applications [1].

97 The production and accumulation of valuable compounds by microalgae is generally
98 related to the environmental conditions and the growth phase, and it often occurs as a
99 response to environmental stresses [2].

100 Modelling the effect of nutrients is of particular interest due to their strong relevance in
101 different microalgal industrial processes: subjecting microalgae to nutrient deprivation
102 stresses is often used to enhance lipid accumulation as well as other valuable
103 compounds [3,4]. For instance, cyanophycin (a molecule that is attracting a lot of
104 interest as a raw material in various industrial sectors) is synthesised by several species
105 of cyanobacteria when they are exposed to nutrient limitations, acting as a reservoir for
106 energy [5]. Understanding nutrient assimilation by microalgae is also essential in
107 wastewater treatment applications, where the main goal is to optimise both nutrient
108 assimilation rates (i.e., nutrient removal from wastewater) and biomass production [6].
109 This is particularly challenging since wastewater is a very heterogeneous nutrient
110 source: nutrient availability in wastewater can be insufficient or pose negative effects
111 on microalgal growth, compromising the commercial viability of the process [7,8]. When
112 it comes to biofuel production from microalgal biomass, special attention must be paid
113 to microalgae biochemical composition (in particular, lipid content), which is also highly
114 affected by nutrient supply [9,10]. Finally, microalgae cultivation represents a promising
115 biomass source to complement agricultural crops; however, it requires considerable
116 amounts of nutrients and thus it is desirable to improve nutrient assimilation efficiency
117 in order to avoid competition for fertiliser supply [11].

118 For these reasons, the availability of mathematical models capable of accurately
119 describing the effect of nutrients on microalgae growth is a key to optimise the design
120 and control of the aforementioned industrial processes [12]

121 The Monod equation and the Droop equation are two of the earliest and most applied
122 models that describe the effect of nutrients on microalgae growth rate (μ). The first

123 relates μ to the dissolved concentration of the limiting nutrient, while the latter relates
124 μ to the intracellular concentration of the limiting nutrient (“cell quota”, q), defined as
125 the amount of internal nutrient per unit of biomass. The Monod equation is
126 conventionally used to describe microalgal growth; however, it is known that microalgae
127 can continue to grow after dissolved nutrients are exhausted, as they have the ability to
128 decouple nutrient uptake from biomass growth [13,14]. The Droop model is able to
129 capture this phenomenon, giving a more accurate description of the effect of nutrients
130 on microalgae growth rate [15].

131 The identification of the Droop model is however challenging: also because of
132 correlation between model parameters, a high number of measurements and
133 experiments is needed to reliably calibrate the model, which results in long and time-
134 consuming experimental campaigns. Furthermore, although steady-state continuous
135 cultures are preferred in terms of microalgal production, working with continuous
136 systems can become highly time consuming, as the transition between different steady
137 states requires time, and several steady states are needed to obtain large set of
138 experimental data for the identification of the parameters related to each nutrient [2].
139 Model-based design of experiments (MBDoe) is a mathematical technique that exploits
140 the knowledge of the system, embedded in the equations of a mathematical model, to
141 plan highly informative experiments for accurate estimation of model parameters [16],
142 [17].

143 MBDoe has been applied successfully in numerous fields: for instance, recently,
144 Fleitmann et al. [18] used MBDoe to minimise the thermodynamic and economic
145 performance metrics of solvent-based processes; De-Luca et al. [19] identified a
146 crystallisation model for pharmaceutical application based on MBDoe approach; and
147 Waldron et al. [20] exploited MBDoe to estimate kinetic parameters in transient flow
148 experiments. In the microalgae field, Bernardi et al. [21] applied MBDoe to address the
149 identification of a state model describing light-limited photosynthetic production in
150 microalgae.

151 In this work, MBDoe is applied to optimise experiments with dynamic input variations
152 of dilution rate and nitrogen concentration for precise parameter estimation of the
153 Droop model. Microalga *Tetradismus obliquus* is used in this study, and data for
154 parameter estimation are obtained from measurements of biomass and nitrogen

155 concentrations. We will demonstrate the MBDoe application allows reducing
156 significantly the experimental effort needed to estimate the parameters of the Droop
157 model in a continuous PBR, and that the calibrated model can be exploited for the
158 reliable representation of the dynamics of nitrogen uptake.

159 This article is organised as follows. Section 2. describes the experimental setup and the
160 modelling framework, including the mathematical foundation of MBDoe. Section 3.
161 presents the experimental results and discusses them critically. Some final remarks and
162 future perspectives conclude the work.

163

164 **2. Materials and methods**

165 **2.1. Microalgal species and cultivation system**

166 *Tetrademus obliquus* 276-7 (obtained from SAG-Goettingen) was cultivated in sterile
167 BG11 medium modified to have a double (2x) concentration of all the nutrients (except
168 for nitrogen concentration, which will be specifically described further in this section)
169 and buffered with HEPES 1M pH 8 to avoid acidification caused by CO₂ bubbling and
170 maintaining the pH between the values of 7 and 8. The exact composition of the original
171 medium (1x) can be found in [22].

172 For each experiment, two vertical panel photobioreactors (PBRs) were run in CSTR
173 (Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor) mode, with a volume of 200 mL and a thickness of
174 35 mm, working at two light intensities: 220 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 420 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, which are
175 limiting and saturating conditions of light, respectively. Performing the same
176 experimental protocol also at a higher light intensity allowed to obtain additional data,
177 increasing the robustness of the estimated parameters with respect to light variations.

178 The medium was pumped into the reactors by means of a multi-channel peristaltic pump
179 (120S/DM3, Watson Marlow, USA), while an overflow exit was placed on the opposite
180 side of the reactors, ensuring a constant liquid level. A thin baffle was added to avoid
181 short-circuiting of the inlet medium flow rate and increase liquid turbulence. Mixing was
182 ensured by a magnetic stirrer placed at the bottom of the reactor, so that the reactor
183 can reasonably considered as a CSTR. A picture and the layout of the experimental
184 apparatus is reported in Appendix A.

185 CO₂ was provided in excess by means of a CO₂-air flow (5% v/v, corresponding to a
186 dissolved concentration of 1.7 mM approximately) supplied through a tube from the

187 bottom of the reactors. The experiments were carried out in a refrigerated incubator,
188 which kept the temperature constant at 24°C. A LED lamp (Light Source SL3500, Photon
189 System Instruments, Czech Republic) was used for light supply, and light intensity was
190 measured by means of an HD of 2102.1 photoradiometer (Delta OHM, Italy).

191

192 **2.2. Analytical procedures**

193 The dilution rate was set by the peristaltic pump and checked twice a day by measuring
194 the volume of liquid in the outlet of the reactors. Biomass concentration was monitored
195 by optical density measurements at 750 nm (OD_{750}), after diluting the samples
196 accordingly so that the OD values fall within the measuring range of the apparatus (from
197 0 to 1). OD_{750} was measured with a UV-Visible double beam spectrophotometer
198 (UV1900, by Shimadzu, Japan). At the end of each experiment, dry weight was
199 determined by filtering 10 mL of the culture sample on a previously dried 0.45 μm
200 nitrocellulose filter with a vacuum flask. The filters were then dried at 110°C in a
201 laboratory oven for at least 2h. This allowed to obtain a correlation between the OD_{750}
202 measurements and the mass concentration of biomass.

203 Nitrogen concentrations were measured by means of an NO_3^- ion selective electrode
204 (perfectION comb NO_3^- , Mettler-Toledo, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland). The inlet
205 nitrogen concentration in the reactors was monitored by analysing a sample of the
206 medium every time a new batch of medium was prepared. To measure nitrogen
207 concentration in the bulk of the reactors, every sample taken from the reactor was
208 filtered with a 0.2 μm filter. All the samples were diluted with deionised water until
209 having a volume of 5 mL with NO_3^- concentrations falling within the measuring range of
210 the electrode (from 1 to 1000 $\text{mg NO}_3^- \text{L}^{-1}$). Before each measurement, 100 μL of ISA
211 (Ionic Strength Adjuster) were added to each sample.

212

213 **2.3. The Droop model**

214 In the Droop model, the specific biomass growth rate μ (d^{-1}) is expressed as a function
215 of both light intensity I ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and the internal quota q ($\text{g}_\text{N} \text{g}_\text{x}^{-1}$) of the limiting
216 nutrient. In this work, nitrogen is the limiting nutrient. According to Bernard [14], the
217 specific biomass growth can be expressed as:

$$218 \quad \mu = \mu_{max} \frac{I}{I + K_I \left(\frac{I}{I_{opt}} - 1 \right)^2} \left(1 - \frac{q_{min}}{q} \right) - k_d \quad . \quad (1)$$

219 In Equation 1, μ_{max} (d^{-1}) is the maximum specific growth rate of the microorganism, K_I
 220 ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is the half-saturation light constant, I_{opt} ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is the optimal light
 221 intensity for microalgae growth, k_d (d^{-1}) is the specific decay rate and q_{min} ($\text{g}_N \text{g}_x^{-1}$) is
 222 the minimum internal nitrogen cell quota. Because of self-shading, light intensity can
 223 vary along the depth of the reactor and for a flat plate reactor it can be expressed
 224 through the Lambert-Beer law:

$$225 \quad I = I_0 \exp(-k_a c_x z) \quad , \quad (2)$$

226 where c_x ($\text{g}_x \text{m}^{-3}$) is biomass concentration, I_0 ($\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) is the incident light intensity
 227 in the PBR, k_a ($\text{m}^{-2} \text{g}_x^{-1}$) is the biomass light absorption coefficient, and z (m) is the spatial
 228 coordinate along the thickness of the reactor. The local biomass growth rate r_x ($\text{g}_x \text{m}^{-3}$
 229 day^{-1}) at z can be expressed as

$$230 \quad r_x = \mu c_x \quad (3)$$

231 and can be averaged along the culture depth W (m) to calculate the average biomass
 232 growth rate r_x^{avg} ($\text{g}_x \text{m}^{-3} \text{day}^{-1}$):

$$233 \quad r_x^{avg} = \frac{1}{W} \int_0^W r_x dz \quad . \quad (4)$$

234 In the Droop model, the limiting nutrient uptake rate ρ ($\text{g}_N \text{g}_x^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) depends both on the
 235 external dissolved nitrogen concentration c_N ($\text{g}_N \text{m}^{-3}$) and on its internal quota according
 236 to [23].

$$237 \quad \rho = \rho_N \frac{c_N}{K_N + c_N} \left(1 - \frac{q}{q_{max}} \right) \quad , \quad (5)$$

238 where ρ_N ($\text{g}_N \text{g}_x^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) is the maximum uptake of the limiting nutrient, K_N ($\text{g}_N \text{m}^{-3}$) is the
 239 limiting nutrient half-saturation constant, and q_{max} ($\text{g}_N \text{g}_x^{-1}$) is the maximum limiting
 240 nutrient quota in the biomass. Material balances for biomass in a continuous PBR are
 241 written as:

$$242 \quad \frac{dc_x}{dt} = \mu(q)c_x - Dc_x \quad , \quad (6)$$

$$243 \quad \frac{dc_N}{dt} = -\rho(c_N)c_x - Dc_N + Dc_{N,in} \quad , \quad (7)$$

244 where D (d^{-1}) is the dilution rate and $c_{N,in}$ ($\text{g}_N \text{m}^{-3}$) is the nitrogen concentration of the
 245 inlet flowrate. The internal nutrient quota is maintained by uptake from external
 246 medium and consumed by cells metabolism. Thus, the material balance of internal
 247 quota can be expressed as:

$$248 \quad \frac{dq}{dt} = \rho(c_N) - \mu(q)q \quad . \quad (8)$$

249 The goal is to estimate Droop parameters K_N , q_{max} , q_{min} , ρ_N , which are mainly related
 250 to the interaction between cells and nitrogen. Parameters μ_{max} , K_I , I_{opt} , k_d , k_a are
 251 related to the effect of light on cell growth: we assume they are not affected by nitrogen
 252 dynamics, and are therefore fixed as in Table 1 based on experiments in a similar reactor
 253 of 3.5 cm thickness and the same species [24].

254 **Table 1:** Fixed light parameters.

Name	Value
μ_{max}	2.8 d^{-1}
K_I	$262.8 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
I_{opt}	$178.3 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$
k_d	0.3 d^{-1}
k_a	$0.09 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ g}_x^{-1}$

255

256 **2.4. Model-based design of experiments**

257 MBDoE is a mathematical technique that, exploiting an *a priori* knowledge embedded in
 258 a mechanistic mathematical model, aims at obtaining the maximum information from
 259 an experiment that will yield, in a statistical sense, the most informative data for
 260 modelling activity avoiding waste of time and resources [17]. With this approach, model
 261 equations and current parameter values are employed to estimate and then maximise
 262 the information content of the experiment.

263 To apply MBDoE, Equations 1-8 can be rearranged in a compact form:

$$264 \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{f}(\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t), \mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t), \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{k}, t) = 0 \\ \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

265 in which \mathbf{x} is the N_x -dimensional vector of the model state variables and $\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t)$ is the
 266 vector of time derivatives, $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = [c_x, c_N]^T$ is the N_y -dimensional vector of measured
 267 response variables, $\mathbf{u} = [D, c_{N,in}]^T$ is the N_u -dimensional set of time-varying inputs to
 268 the system, $\boldsymbol{\theta} = [K_N, q_{max}, q_{min}, \rho_N]^T$ is the N_θ -dimensional vector of parameters to be
 269 estimated, $\mathbf{k} = [\mu_{max}, K_I, k_d, k_a, I, W]^T$ the N_k -dimensional vector of constants of the
 270 model and $0 < t < \tau$ is time, with τ as the total duration of the experiment. Symbol $\hat{\cdot}$ is
 271 employed to define the estimate of a variable: e.g. $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ represents the vector of model
 272 parameter estimates. Samplings times are collected in the N_{sp} -dimensional vector \mathbf{t}_{sp} .
 273 Each experiment is thus mathematically defined by the experiment design vector $\boldsymbol{\phi} =$
 274 $[\mathbf{u}(t), \mathbf{t}_{sp}, \tau]^T$.

275 Mathematically, the improvement in the precision of parameter estimates determines
 276 a decrease in the size of the inference regions of the parameters. This can be formally
 277 interpreted as a decrease in the value of the elements of the parameters variance-
 278 covariance matrix \mathbf{V} [17], which depends on the model structure (i.e. model equations,
 279 and correlation between inputs and outputs). In practical terms, an optimal experiment
 280 is characterised by an experiment design vector $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ (i.e. optimal dynamic profiles of input
 281 variables, optimal timing of sampling points, and optimal experiment duration) that
 282 maximises a metric of the information that can be collected from the experiment.
 283 According to the so-called D-criterion [25], which is employed in this work, the optimal
 284 experiment is the one that maximises the experimental information content by
 285 minimizing the determinant of the \mathbf{V} matrix. Additional details about MBDofE
 286 formulation are given in Appendix B.

287 For experimental practical feasibility, the length of the experiments was set to 8 days,
 288 and the vector of sampling times was fixed as well: measurements of both biomass
 289 nitrogen concentration were taken at 9:00 and 17:00 from day 1 to 5 and on day 8; the
 290 final measurement was on day 9 at 9:00. Control intervals were also set: input variables
 291 were allowed to vary immediately after sampling times.

292 Constraints were imposed on both input and output variables based on the
 293 experimental apparatus. The dilution rate interval was set as 0.01 - 1.78 d^{-1} , with the
 294 upper bound value to avoid regions of experimental instability, while the inlet nitrogen
 295 concentration interval was set as 10 - 1000 mg L^{-1} . For output variables, nitrogen

296 concentration was allowed to vary in the interval 0.3-10000 mg L⁻¹; the lower bound was
297 set accordingly to the lower measurement limit of the nitrate probe of 1 mg L⁻¹ of NO₃⁻
298 (corresponding to 0.23 mg L⁻¹ of N).

299 Although measurements of internal nitrogen quota were not performed in this work,
300 initial values were required to solve differential equations. Thus, the initial values for the
301 internal nitrogen quota used for the calculations were estimated according to equation:

$$302 \quad q = \frac{c_{N,in} - c_N}{c_x} \quad . \quad (10)$$

303 The outcomes of MBDoE are piece-wise constant profiles of the input variables for
304 optimal experiments. To specifically account for experimental constraints, input
305 variables were kept constant considering control intervals of 8 hours (from 9:00 to
306 17:00) and 16 hours (from 17:00 to 9:00 of the following day) for each day, except days
307 6 and 7, where a single constant value was used.

308 A sequential approach is adopted, where three consecutive steps are needed to
309 determine the model parameters: (1) the design of a new set of experiments, based on
310 current knowledge and on the maximisation of the information content of the
311 experiment; (2) the execution of the designed experiment and collection of new data;
312 and (3) the estimation of new model parameters and their statistical assessment. The
313 accuracy of the estimated parameters is statistically assessed through a *t*-test (for more
314 details see Appendix B).

315 If the estimation is not precise, the whole procedure is repeated until a satisfactory
316 parameter precision is attained. Each estimation task is based on all available data up to
317 that point.

318 MBDoE and parameter estimation tasks were performed using software gPROMS v7.0.7
319 by Siemens Process Systems Engineering.

320

321 **3. Results**

322 **3.1. Sensitivity analysis**

323 Model practical identifiability, i.e., the possibility to estimate the model parameters
324 considering the actual experimental conditions, is a key preliminary requirement. Local
325 sensitivity analysis is a simple test for assessing the model practical identifiability [26]
326 where dynamic trajectories of the measured output variables are obtained by

327 perturbing the parameters to be estimated one-at-a-time. The dynamic sensitivity
 328 $s_{i,p}(t)$ for the i^{th} variable perturbed by the p^{th} parameter at time t is computed as:

$$329 \quad s_{i,p}(t) = \frac{\hat{y}_i(t) - \hat{y}_{i,p}^{pert}(t)}{\Delta\% \hat{y}_{i,REF}} \quad , \quad (11)$$

330 where $\hat{y}_i(t)$ is the value calculated with the nominal parametric set, $\hat{y}_{i,p}^{pert}(t)$ is the
 331 perturbed value calculated with the variation in the p^{th} parameter, $\Delta\%$ is the
 332 percentage perturbation of the parameter (here set equal to 1% for all parameters) and
 333 $\hat{y}_{i,REF}$ is a reference value for normalisation. In other words, local sensitivity analysis
 334 measures how the measured model responses are affected by a variation in the
 335 parameter value during an experiment, and accordingly, if the dynamics of a measured
 336 variable are informative on the parameter value and can be exploited for its estimation.
 337 Two simulated experiments with two step perturbations for the dilution rate and the
 338 inlet nitrogen concentration were used for the sensitivity analysis. The input profiles and
 339 results of the sensitivity analysis are shown in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 1(c), q_{min}
 340 appears to be the parameter with the highest impact on the biomass concentration and
 341 thus its estimation is expected to be linked to this measurement. K_N , q_{max} , ρ_N have a
 342 minor impact on biomass concentration, but Figure 1(d), shows that their main effect is
 343 on the nitrogen concentration; thus, this variable is expected to be mainly responsible
 344 for their estimation. In Figure 1(d) the nearly symmetric profiles for K_N and q_{max}
 345 indicate that there is anticorrelation between those parameters, and hint that possible
 346 issues may arise in their estimation. It can be observed that there is some correlation,
 347 too, between q_{max} and ρ_N . However, the analysis suggests that measurements of
 348 biomass and nitrogen concentration are sufficient for precise estimation of all Droop
 349 parameters if experiments are planned adequately.

350

351 **3.2. Optimal experiments and parameters estimation**

352 As discussed in Section 2.4., MBDoe was applied in an iterative procedure involving
 353 experiments and parameters estimation. As a result, two optimally designed
 354 experiments were performed, and the experimental data were employed for two
 355 subsequent parameters estimations.

356 For the first optimal experiment, Figure 2 shows the theoretical (expected from MBDoE)
357 and real profiles of input variables, and Figure 3 a comparison between experimental
358 profiles and model predictions of the output variables after the second and final
359 parameter estimation for both light conditions. Similarly, the second optimal
360 experiment is shown in Figures 4-5, with profiles of input variables in Figure 4 and output
361 variables in Figure 5. Table 2 summarises the two parameter estimations with the
362 corresponding t -values: the first estimation was performed after completing the first
363 experiment and used as the parametric guess for the second MBDoE; the second (and
364 final) estimation was performed after the second experiment, employing data from both
365 the first and second experiment. Notice that in Figure 2b and Figure 4b the experimental
366 nitrogen concentration is the same for both light conditions since the nitrogen source is
367 the same.

368 Some mismatch between theoretical and real profiles for dilution rate and inlet nitrogen
369 concentration can be seen in Figure 2a-b and Figure 4a-b. This not surprising as real
370 experimental conditions can deviate from the theoretical ones due to external
371 disturbances and technological limitations of the experimental apparatus (e.g., clogging
372 of tubes, malfunctioning of the pumping or electrical system). For this reason, not only
373 the output (biomass concentration, c_x , and nitrogen concentration in the PBR, c_N) but
374 also the input variables (D and $c_{N,in}$) have been measured to obtain their true
375 experimental values and ensure that the parameter estimation is performed with the
376 most accurate information.

377 For the first experiment, the experimental profile of biomass concentration is higher in
378 the PBR with higher illumination (Figure 3b). The difference between initial conditions
379 for both reactors is due to the operation in continuous mode. In continuous systems,
380 only the input variables (i.e. dilution rate, inlet nutrients concentrations, light intensity)
381 are manipulated, while values of variables inside the PBR (i.e. biomass and nitrogen
382 concentration) change in response to those inputs. Dynamic profiles of measured
383 variables are thus deeply affected by the operation mode, either batch or continuous,
384 and it was shown that a continuous PBR arrangement strongly influences both biomass
385 productivity and nutrient uptake [8]. Apart from the initial values, the different
386 illumination intensities do not have a major effect on the experimental dynamic
387 trajectories of nitrogen concentration in Figure 3c-d, which are similar for both the

388 reactors. As regards the dynamics of input variables, the dilution rate drops to values
 389 close to zero between day 1 and 2 (Figure 2a): in this time interval, PBRs are practically
 390 in batch mode, as reflected by the sharp increase in biomass concentration between day
 391 1 and 2 in Figure 3a-b, typical of batch systems. Despite this fact, the experimental
 392 nitrogen concentration in the PBRs remains almost constant between day 1 and 2
 393 (Figure 3c-d), showing a certain degree of inertia for the system. This behaviour can be
 394 explained with the consumption of internal nitrogen reservoirs between day 1 and 2,
 395 when the supply of nitrogen to PBRs is almost zero. In fact, it is well known that
 396 microalgae can internally store nutrients when they are in non-limiting concentration
 397 and use these internal reservoirs for growth in nutrients-depleted conditions [13]. This
 398 decoupling between biomass growth and nitrogen uptake can result in an inertial
 399 behaviour of the system [13], also observed for other nutrients [8].

400 The second and third columns of Table 2 show the parameter estimates after the first
 401 optimal experiment. It can be noticed that only one parameter, q_{min} , is estimated with
 402 precision, while the t -values of the others are below the reference value. This reflects the
 403 outcome of the sensitivity analysis in Figure 1c, where q_{min} had the highest impact on
 404 measured biomass concentration, and was therefore expected to be relatively easy to
 405 estimate.

406

407 **Table 2:** Estimated model parameters. Reference t -value is equal to 1.68 for first and
 408 1.66 for second fitting; t -values marked with * indicate estimates with a t -values below
 409 the threshold.

Parameter	First fit	First fit 95% t -value	Second fit	Second fit 95% t -value
K_N [g _N m ⁻³]	2.88	1.65*	0.70	1.75
q_{max} [g _N g _x ⁻¹]	0.1390	1.39*	0.1080	3.39
q_{min} [g _N g _x ⁻¹]	0.0051	1.95	0.0051	5.83
ρ_N [g _N g _x ⁻¹ d ⁻¹]	0.076	1.53*	0.237	2.00

410

411 Figures 4-5 show the theoretical and experimental profiles in the second optimal
412 experiment. As shown in Figure 4a, the second experiment is conducted at very high
413 values of dilution rate (app. $1.7\text{-}2\text{ d}^{-1}$), close to washout conditions. Moreover, apart
414 from a sharp peak around day 7, inlet nitrogen concentration of Figure 4b is almost at
415 zero for the entire duration of the experiment. These experiments can thus represent
416 conditions of nitrogen starvation, as shown in Figure 5c-d, where the nitrogen
417 concentration inside PBRs drops to values close to zero after day 2 and remains at that
418 level for most of the experimental time.

419 The difference in experimental biomass concentration profiles found in Figure 3a-b for
420 the two lights is considerably reduced for the second experiment, as shown in Figure 5a-
421 b, highlighting that under extreme nutrient depletion the key factor limiting biomass
422 productivity is nitrogen concentration [11]. Moreover, experimental biomass
423 concentration remains almost constant: even if nitrogen concentration in the reactors
424 is almost equal to zero after day 2 (Figure 5c-d), biomass concentration has a slight
425 increase for both reactors between day 2 and 5, and it decreases only after day 7. This
426 shows again how the consumption of the internal nitrogen content is critical for
427 sustaining microalgae growth and highlights the dependence of biomass productivity on
428 the internal quota [7]. This is a key phenomenon to consider to fully capture nutrients
429 dynamics, and it confirms the need to employ the Droop model instead of a traditional
430 Monod-like one [7,8,13].

431 Data from both optimal experiments were employed for the second parameter
432 estimation, shown in the last two columns of Table 2. Adding a second optimal
433 experiment allows for a precise estimation of all the parameters. Between the first and
434 second estimation, the highest variation is recorded for K_N and ρ_N , that also have the
435 lowest t -values among the parameters. This could be caused by the correlation between
436 K_N and ρ_N highlighted from the sensitivity analysis in Figure 1d, which makes a precise
437 estimation more difficult. To conclude, Table 2 shows two optimal experiments to be
438 sufficient for precise parameters estimation. In particular, a significant result is that
439 MBDoE allows for precise estimation of the maximum (q_{max}) and minimum (q_{min})
440 quotas, whose identification through direct experimental measurements is known to be
441 a challenging task [13].

442 Parameters from Table 2 were compared to other estimations for similar microalgae
443 strains, such as *S. obliquus* RISE [27], *S. obliquus* [28], and a consortium of *Chlorella*
444 *sorokiniana* and *Scenedesmus* sp. [29]. It should be stated, however, that very few works
445 deal with the estimation of Droop model parameters for the genus *Scenedesmus*
446 (homotypic synonym of *Tetradesmus*); moreover, literature data are often obtained in
447 conventional batch systems. It can be observed that our estimate of parameter q_{max}
448 ($0.1390 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$) falls within the range from $0.099 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$ [28] to $0.1806 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$ [29] as
449 reported in the literature, while q_{min} ($0.0051 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$) is outside the range of $0.011 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$
450 1 [28] to $0.047 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1}$ [27]. However, it should be remarked that q_{min} is the parameter
451 most affecting the measured output (see the sensitivity analysis), and therefore the one
452 that is more precisely and reliably estimated as confirmed by the high value in the t -test.
453 We are therefore confident about the reliability of the estimated obtained in this work.
454 The estimated values of parameters K_N and ρ_N are within the literature range
455 (respectively, from $0.020 \text{ g}_N \text{ m}^{-3}$ [28] to $12.61 \text{ g}_N \text{ m}^{-3}$ [29], and from $0.0597 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ to
456 $2.95 \text{ g}_N \text{ g}_x^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ [29]), but intervals are so wide that a comparison is hardly meaningful.
457 The large variability in the K_N and ρ_N estimates from the literature is not surprising since
458 their correlation can make their estimation a difficult task. The fact that by using MBDoE
459 it was possible to achieve a statistically sound estimation of both parameters is a valuable
460 result, and further demonstrates the effectiveness of the methodology and the
461 importance of designing experiments in such a way as to maximise their information
462 content.

463 Fitting results of the second parameter estimation are shown in Figure 3 for the first and
464 in Figure 5 for the second experiment. Both figures highlight an overall good agreement
465 between experimental data and model prediction, although some mismatch exists. The
466 mismatch can be partly caused from limitations of the experimental apparatus (e.g.,
467 there was a malfunctioning in the mixing system during the second experiment at 420
468 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, concerning biomass experimental points 4-6). However, it could also
469 highlight limitations of the model in capturing the dynamic behaviour of the system. As
470 an example, in the first experiment, nitrogen experimental points 2-6 for both reactors
471 (Figure 3c-d) show that the experimental system has a certain degree of “inertia” that
472 the model only partly describes.

473 Overall, model fitting is better in conditions of nutrients scarcity as the ones in the
474 second experiment (Figures 4-5). For the first experiment, fitting of data at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
475 $^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ is generally better than at $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$: e.g., biomass concentration at $420 \mu\text{mol}$
476 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ in Figure 3b tends to be underestimated. This may denote an interaction between
477 the effects of light and nitrogen [30] that the model cannot represent.

478

479 **3.3. Model validation and discussion**

480 Two additional experiments were performed to validate the model through the
481 comparison of data with model simulations at the same experimental conditions. These
482 experiments were performed at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, with an
483 approximate duration of 1.5 and 2.5 days respectively, and with varying dilution rates.
484 Figure 6 shows profiles of the input variables for both experiments and Figure 7 the
485 comparison between experimental data and model prediction for biomass (Figure 7 a-
486 b) and nitrogen concentration (Figure 7 c-d). The objective of the validating experiments
487 was to challenge the model and to assess whether it was capable of capturing fast
488 dynamic variations in the system, which were not considered during the calibration step.
489 Thus, in addition to step change input variations of the dilution rate, nitrogen inlet pulses
490 were also directly injected in the PBRs as shown in Figure 6b. Nitrogen pulses with the
491 desired concentration were delivered to PBRs by manual pipetting of small volumes (1-
492 2 ml approximately) of solution at given time instants. Nitrogen pulses also have a minor
493 effect on the dilution rate profile, as shown in Figure 6a: despite their low volume (1 ml
494 per pulse), nitrogen inlet pulses cause an increase in the dilution rate since they are
495 delivered in a very short time. Inlet nitrogen pulses mainly affect the nitrogen
496 concentration in the PBRs (Figure 7c-d), while biomass concentration has slower
497 variations (Figure 7a-b), affected principally by the dilution rate and the nitrogen
498 concentration of the inlet flowrate. Biomass experimental profile at $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ is
499 considerably higher than at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and model prediction accounts for this
500 difference as shown in Figure 7a-b. Moreover, as shown in Figure 7c-d, the model
501 simulation can capture both slow and fast nitrogen dynamics derived from inlet pulses.
502 To summarise, prediction performances of the calibrated model are generally good as
503 shown in Figure 7. In particular, the close agreement between experimental data and
504 model prediction in the validation experiment (mean root square error, %MRSE, of 4%

505 for biomass and 11% for nitrogen) proves that the model is capable to follow both fast
506 and slow variations in the system. With all the experiments being performed in low
507 nitrogen or nitrogen deprivation conditions (Figures 2,4,6) the model proved to be
508 suitable for application in nutrients-scarcity conditions and it can be used to represent
509 dynamic conditions (e.g. for process optimisation purposes).

510 However, note that, especially for long time spans like those in Figures 3,5, the
511 experimental system can show an inertial behaviour toward conditions of nitrogen
512 deprivation. This behaviour is only partially captured in the model prediction: this could
513 be a sign that the mathematical structure of the Droop model is too simple and a
514 structural modification of the model itself is needed to account for this inertia, which
515 may be related to acclimation dynamics, which are not accounted for in the standard
516 model formulation.

517 Moreover, in this work, light conditions were kept constants in the experiments at
518 values in the range of photosaturation, since this is generally the most favourable
519 condition for microalgae cultivation. As shown in Figures 3,5,7, the model can predict
520 well the experimental behaviour at both light intensities employed. However, a minor
521 discrepancy between predictions of the biomass concentrations in the first optimal
522 experiment (Figure 3 b) can highlight possible interaction between the effects of light
523 and nitrogen variations on cells.

524 Results from this work also showed that the application of MBDoE for dynamic
525 experiments can allow reducing the experimental effort required to estimate the Droop
526 model parameters. For instance, if we consider the experimental set up used in this work
527 and rely on steady-state conditions only as in [2], we estimated that the experimental
528 campaign would require over two months instead of 16 days as in this case.

529

530 **Conclusions**

531 Model-based design of experiments was employed to estimate the Droop model
532 parameters for microalga *Tetradismus obliquus* cultivated in a continuous
533 photobioreactor. It was demonstrated how the design of optimal experiments based on
534 the model structure and capable of maximizing the information experiment allowed to:

- 535 1. estimate all model parameters in a statistically satisfactory way, even if some
536 parameters were affected by high correlation;

537 2. limit the duration of the experimental campaign to only two 8-days optimal
538 dynamic experiments, thus avoiding the need of a large number of time and
539 resource consuming experiments.

540 The identified model proved to be able to represent the dynamics of both calibration
541 and validation experiments with good accuracy, also highlighting some potential
542 shortcomings of the Droop model itself, particularly for slow phenomena. The model is
543 nonetheless able to capture the behaviour of the system, and to represent the dynamics
544 of nitrogen uptake effectively.

545 Future work will aim at testing the model for optimisation purposes, and extending its
546 description accuracy by incorporating additional phenomena, particularly with concern
547 to slow dynamics.

548

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554

555 **Appendix A**

556 Figure A1 represents a scheme of the experimental setup used during all experiments,
557 while Figure A2 shows a photography of both reactors taken during one of the
558 experiments.

559

560 **Appendix B**

561 Mathematically, the decrease of the size of the inference regions of the model
562 parameters allows the improvement of parametric precision. This is equal to decreasing
563 the value of the elements of the parameter variance-covariance matrix \mathbf{V} , which can be
564 defined as in [25]:

$$565 \mathbf{V}(\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \boldsymbol{\phi}) = \left[\sum_i^{N_y} \sum_j^{N_y} s_{ij} \mathbf{Q}_i^T \mathbf{Q}_j \right]^{-1} \quad (\text{B1})$$

566 with

$$567 \mathbf{Q}_i = \left. \frac{\partial \hat{y}_i}{\partial \theta_m} \right|_{t_i} \quad l = 1, \dots, N_{sp} \quad m = 1, \dots, N_{\theta} \quad . \quad (\text{B2})$$

568 In Equation B1, Q_i is the ($N_{sp} \times N_\theta$) dynamic sensitivity matrix of the i^{th} response
 569 variable. The term s_{ij} in Equation B1 is the element (i, j) of the inverse of the
 570 experimental error variance-covariance matrix. Here, a constant relative variance error
 571 model was adopted:

$$572 \sigma_{y_i}^2 = (\alpha \hat{y}_i)^2, \quad (B3)$$

573 where \hat{y}_i is the response i and $\sigma_{y_i}^2$ is its variance. Values of α employed in this work were
 574 retrieved from preliminary measurements and are shown in Table B1.

575

576 **Table B1:** Error model parameters.

Parameter	Biomass concentration	Nitrogen concentration
α	0.1 [-]	0.08 [-]

577

578 The final designed experiment ϕ^{opt} was then calculated as the solution of the
 579 minimisation/maximisation problem:

$$580 \phi^{opt} = \operatorname{argmin} \{ \det[\mathbf{V}(\hat{\theta}, \phi)] \} = \operatorname{argmin} \{ \det[\mathbf{V}^{-1}(\hat{\theta}, \phi)] \} \quad (B4)$$

581 defined according to the so-called D-criterion [25]. The optimum experiment is thus the
 582 one that minimises the parametric uncertainty and maximises the experimental
 583 information content.

584 After parameter estimation, it is possible to obtain a statistical metric of parameter
 585 precision for the i^{th} parameter by computing a Student t -value [31]:

$$586 t_i = \frac{\hat{\theta}_i}{\sqrt{V_{ii}}} \quad (B5)$$

587 where V_{ii} is the i^{th} diagonal element of \mathbf{V} . The t -value can be tested against a reference
 588 t -distribution with $(n-p)$ degrees of freedom, where n is the total number of
 589 experimental observations and p is the number of parameters [17]. If the t -values are
 590 higher than the reference ones, then the estimation is considered reliable, while t -values
 591 lower than the reference value show estimates with low statistical significance. In
 592 models involving multiple parameters, a low t -value can be caused by high correlation
 593 between parameters [17].

594

595

596

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- 692
- 693

694 **Figure captions**

695 **Figure 1:** Dynamic sensitivity analysis: dilution rate (a) and inlet nitrogen concentration
696 (b) input profiles; sensitivities of model parameters on biomass (c) and nitrogen
697 concentration (d).

698

699 **Figure 2:** Input profiles of the first optimal experiment; (a) comparison between
700 theoretical and experimental dilution rates at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
701 (b) comparison between theoretical and experimental inlet nitrogen concentration.

702

703 **Figure 3:** Output profiles of the first optimal experiment; comparison between
704 experimental and final fitting profiles of biomass concentration at (a) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
705 and (b) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; comparison between experimental and final fitting profiles of
706 nitrogen concentration at (c) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and (d) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

707

708 **Figure 4:** Input profiles of the second optimal experiment; (a) comparison between
709 theoretical and experimental dilution rates at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
710 (b) comparison between theoretical and experimental inlet nitrogen concentration.

711

712 **Figure 5:** Output profiles of the second optimal experiment; comparison between
713 experimental and final fitting profiles of biomass concentration at (a) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
714 and (b) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; comparison between experimental and final fitting profiles of
715 nitrogen concentration at (c) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and (d) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

716

717 **Figure 6:** Input variables of validation experiments at $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
718 (a) dilution factor; (b) inlet nitrogen concentration.

719

720 **Figure 7:** Model validation results; comparison between experimental and predicted
721 profiles of biomass concentration at (a) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and (b) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$;
722 comparison between experimental and predicted profiles of nitrogen concentration at
723 (c) $220 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and (d) $420 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

724

725 **Figure A1:** Figure A1. Scheme of the experimental setup

726 **Figure A2:** Photography of the reactors during one of the experiments.